

RP-HPLC Method development, validation and stability indicating studies for simultaneous estimation of Anastrozole and Temozolomide in bulk and its pharmaceutical formulations.

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ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, precise, sensitive and reproducible reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method has been developed for the quantitative analysis of Anastrozole and Temozolomide in pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatographic separation of Anastrozole and Temozolomide was achieved on by using Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C18 (15cmX4.6mm,5 μ m) column and the mobile phase Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (0.02 M, pH 2.5) and Acetonitrile containing in the ratio of 66:34% v/v. The retention times for Anastrozole and Temozolomide were found to be 9.93 and 2.02 min respectively. Linearity was established for Anastrozole and Temozolomide in the range of 0-50 μ g/ml respectively, with correlation coefficient (r^2) for both the drugs are 0.997 and 0.999. Anastrozole and Temozolomide were found to have %RSDs of 0.0848 and 0.7684 respectively, for Repeatability. Accuracy was carried out in triplicate, and the percentage recovery 99.67, 99.19, 99.49 % for Temozolomide and 99.92, 100.72, 100.40% for Anastrozole. The limit for mean % recovery is 98-102% and as both the values are within the limit, hence it can be said that the proposed method was accurate. The flow rate was 1.0 ml/min; detection was carried out by absorption at 294 nm using a photodiode array detector at ambient temperature. The number of theoretical plates and tailing factor for Anastrozole and Temozolomide were NLT 2000 and should not more than 2 respectively. % Relative standard deviation of peak areas of all measurements always less than 2.0. The proposed method was validated according to ICH guidelines. The method was found to be simple, economical, suitable, precise, accurate & robust method for quantitative analysis of Anastrozole and Temozolomide and study of its stability.

Key words: HPLC, Anastrozole and Temozolomide

I.INTRODUCTION:

Anastrozole selectively inhibits aromatase. The principal source of circulating estrogen (primarily estradiol) is conversion of adrenally-generated androstenedione to estrone by aromatase in peripheral tissues. Therefore, aromatase inhibition leads to a decrease in serum and tumor concentration of estrogen, leading to a decreased tumor mass or delayed progression of tumor growth in some women. Anastrozole has no detectable effect on synthesis of adrenal corticosteroids, aldosterone, and thyroid hormone.

Temozolomide is not active until it is converted at physiologic pH to MTIC. It is suggested that MTIC then alkylates DNA at the N7 position of guanine, O3 position of adenosine, and O6 position of guanosine, with the most common site being the N7 position. This methylation of guanine residues lead to single and double-strand DNA breaks and subsequent apoptotic cell death. It is suggested that the N7-methylguanine plays a critical role in the antitumor activity of the drug, as there is a correlation between the sensitivity of tumor cell lines to temozolomide and the activity of O6-alkylguanine alkyltransferase, which is the DNA repair protein that specifically removes alkyl groups at the O6 position of guanine. Cells lines that have lower levels of AGT are more sensitive to the cytotoxicity of temozolomide. It is also suggested that cytotoxic mechanism of temozolomide is related to the failure of the DNA MMR system to find a complementary base for methylated guanine. The DNA MMR system is involved in the formation of a number of proteins that remove methylated guanine. Evidence shows that when this repair process is targeted to the DNA strand opposite the O6-methylguanine, its inability to find the correct target leads to long-lived nicks in the DNA. The accumulation of these nicks lead to the inhibition of replication in the daughter cells, thereby blocking the cell cycle at the G₂-M boundary. It is used to treat certain types of Breast cancer.. It is a chemotherapy drug that works by slowing cancer cell growth. In some patients, temozolomide decreases the size of brain tumors.

The present study is to develop a stability indicating RP-HPLC method for ANA and TMZ. The objective of the study is to subject the drugs for acid, base, peroxide, light, thermal degradation and estimate its extent of degradation. A Literature survey reveals that several analytical methods for the estimation of ANA and TMZ were reported.

Although different analytical methods are available, a more economical stability indicating analytical method was developed for estimation of Anastrozole and Temozolomide We have forcefully degraded the drugs (standards) under different stress conditions and developed an HPLC method that can differentiate the pure drug from its degradants. The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guideline entitled “Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products” requires that stress testing be carried out to elucidate the inherent.

Fig.1:Chemical structure of Anastrozole

Fig.2: Chemical structure of Temozolomide

A. Chemicals and Reagents**Table 1.** Chemicals and reagents

S.NO	Name	Specifications		Manufacturer/Supplier
		Purity	Grade	
1.	Doubled distilled water	----	----	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
2.	Methanol	99.9%	A.R.	Loba Chem; Mumbai.
3.	Sodium Hydroxide	96%	L.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
4.	Acetonitrile	99.9%	HPLC	Loba Chem; Mumbai.
5.	Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate	99.9	L.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
6.	orthophosphoric acid	99.9	L.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai

B. Instruments and Analytical columns:**Table 2.** Name of the Instruments

S.NO.	Name of Instrument	Instrument Model	Name of manufacturer
1	UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer	UV 1800	Elico India
2	HPLC	1575	Hitachi LaChrome
3	Ultra sonicator	-----	Entrech electronics limited
4	Melting point apparatus	-----	

C. Preparation of standard solution of Temozolomide

10 mg of Temozolomide was weighed accurately and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask. About 10 ml of HPLC grade methanol was added and sonicated to dissolve. The volume was made up to the mark with same solvent. The final solution contained about 30 µg/ml of Temozolomide.

Preparation of standard solution of Anastrozole

10 mg of Anastrozole was weighed accurately and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask. About 10 ml of HPLC grade methanol was added and sonicated to dissolve. The volume was made up to the mark with same solvent. The final solution contained about 30 µg/ml of Anastrozole.

Preparation of mix. standard solution of Temozolomide and Anastrozole

Accurately weighed 25 mg of Temozolomide and 25 mg of Anastrozole were transferred to 25 ml volumetric flask. About 5 ml of HPLC grade methanol was added and sonicated to dissolve. The volume was made up to mark with same solvent. Then 3 ml of the above solution was diluted to 100 ml with the solvent system. The resultant solution was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter and degassed under ultrasonic bath prior to use. From the above standard solution several working standard solutions are prepared by serial dilution technique.

Preparation of mobile phase

Mobile phase was prepared by taking acetonitrile: potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (0.02M, pH 2.5) (34:66v/v). Mobile phase was filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filter and degassed under ultrasonic bath prior to use. The mobile phase was pumped through the column at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min.

II.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A. Method development and optimization:

The choice of the detection wavelength was based on the scanned absorption spectrum of Anastrozole and Temozolomide 10mg of drugs were dissolved in 100ml of methanol separately. The UV spectrum of was Anastrozole and Temozolomide separately scanned in the wave length range 200-400nm. After correlation of the spectrum 273nm wavelength was selected for analysis. (Fig.3a &3b). Trails were performed by using different mobile phases finally resolution was good, theoretical plate count and symmetry were appropriate. Also, no unwanted little peaks were seen between two peaks. Hence it was acceptable. The selected and optimized mobile phase was acetonitrile: potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (0.02M, pH 2.5) (66:34v/v) and conditions optimized were: flow rate (1.0 ml/minute), wavelength (273 nm), Run time was 14 min. Here the peaks were separated and showed better resolution, theoretical plate count and symmetry. The proposed chromatographic conditions were found appropriate for the quantitative determination of the drugs. Temozolomide and Anastrozole RT were found to be 2.02 min &9.93 min .

Fig 3a: UV spectrum of Temozolomide

Fig 3b: UV- spectrum of Anastrozole

Fig 4: Optimized chromatogram

TEMOZOLOMIDE (RT=2.02 min) and ANASTRAZOLE (RT= 9.93 min).

Table 3: Trails for different method

Sl. No	Column Used	Mobile Phase	Flow Rate	Wave length	Observation	Result
1	Waters C ₁₈ , 5 μ m, 25cmx4.6mm i.d.	Methanol: Water = 80: 20	1.0 ml/min	273 Nm	Low response	Method rejected
2	Waters C ₁₈ , 5 μ m, 25cmx4.6mm i.d.	ACN: Water = 40 :60	1.0 ml/min	273 Nm	Broken peak	Method rejected
3	Waters C ₁₈ , 5 μ m, 25cmx4.6mm i.d.	ACN: water = 5: 5	1.0 ml/min	273 Nm	Tailing peak	Method rejected
4	Waters C ₁₈ , 5 μ m, 25cmx4.6mm i.d.	ACN: acetate buffer = 5:5	1.0 ml/ min	273 Nm	Broad Peak	Method rejected
5	Waters C ₁₈ , 5 μ m, 25cmx4.6mm i.d.	ACN: phosphate buffer = 34:66	1.0 ml/min	273 Nm	Nice peak	Method Accepted

B. System Suitability Parameter:

System suitability testing is an integral part of many analytical procedures. The tests are based on the concept that the equipment, electronics, analytical operations and samples to be analyzed constitute an integral system that can be evaluated as such. Following system suitability test parameters were established. The data are shown in Table 4

Table 4: Data of System Suitability Parameter

S.No.	Parameter	Limit	Result
1	Resolution	$R_s > 2$	9.15
2	Asymmetry	$T \leq 2$	Temozolomide=0.12 Anastrozole =0.5
3	Theoretical plate	$N > 2000$	Temozolomide=3246 Anastrozole= 4693

C. Specificity**Preparation and running of synthetic mixture of Temozolomide & anastrozole**

For the specificity of the method the marketed formulations has been taken & The solution was injected into the HPLC system. The chromatograms obtained are shown in

D. Linearity:

Linearity range was found to be 0-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Temozolomide and 0-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Anastrozole. The correlation coefficients were found to be 0.999 & 0.997, the slopes were found to be 44623 & 13801 and intercept were found to be 10569 & 10378 for Temozolomide and Anastrozole respectively.

Table 5: Linearity for Anastrozole and Temozolomide

	Anastrozole	Temozolomide
CONC.	AUC	AUC
0	0	0
10	1228747	424838
20	2638031	904737
30	3983572	1302869
40	5249436	1746831
50	6979310	2250813

Fig 5a: Standard curve for Temozolomide

Fig 5b: Standard curve for Anastrozole

E. Accuracy:

To determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by adding different amounts (80%, 100%, and 120%) of pure drug of Temozolomide were taken and added to the pre-analyzed formulation of concentration 10 μ g/ml. From that percentage recovery values were calculated.

Table 6a: Accuracy results of Temozolomide

Sample ID	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		%Recovery of	Statistical Analysis
	Pure drug	Formulation	Pure drug	
S ₁ : 80 %	8	10	99.63	Mean= 99.67667% S.D. = 0.223681 % R.S.D.= 0.224407
S ₂ : 80 %	8	10	99.92	
S ₃ : 80 %	8	10	99.48	
S ₄ : 100 %	10	10	99.19	Mean= 99.19% S.D. = 0.06 % R.S.D.= 0.06049
S ₅ : 100 %	10	10	99.25	
S ₆ : 100 %	10	10	99.13	
S ₇ : 120 %	12	10	99.25	Mean= 99.49% S.D. = 0.219317 % R.S.D. = 0.220441
S ₈ : 120 %	12	10	99.54	
S ₉ : 120 %	12	10	99.68	

To determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by adding different amounts (80%, 100%, and 120%) of pure drug of Anastrozole were taken and added to the pre-analyzed formulation of concentration 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. From that percentage recovery values were calculated.

Table 6b: Accuracy results of Anastrozole

Sample ID	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)		%Recovery of	Statistical Analysis
	Pure drug	Formulation	Pure drug	
S ₁ : 80 %	8	10	100.23	Mean= 99.92% S.D. = 0.469361268 % R.S.D.=0.469737058
S ₂ : 80 %	8	10	100.15	
S ₃ : 80 %	8	10	99.38	
S ₄ : 100 %	10	10	99.78	Mean= 100.7266667% S.D. = 1.570902076 % R.S.D.=1.559569207
S ₅ : 100 %	10	10	99.86	
S ₆ : 100 %	10	10	102.54	
S ₇ : 120 %	12	10	99.89	Mean= 100.4066667% S.D. = 1.398511113 % R.S.D. = 1.392846869
S ₈ : 120 %	12	10	99.34	
S ₉ : 120 %	12	10	101.99	

Result & Discussion: The mean recoveries were found to be 99.67, 99.19, 99.49 % for Temozolomide and 99.92, 100.72, 100.40% for Anastrozole. The limit for mean % recovery is 98-102% and as both the values are within the limit, hence it can be said that the proposed method was accurate.

F.PRECISION:

Repeatability

The precision of each method was ascertained separately from the peak areas obtained by actual determination of six replicates of a fixed amount of drug. Anastrozole & Temozolomide. The percent relative standard deviations were calculated for Anastrozole & Temozolomide.

Table7a: Data showing repeatability analysis for Anastrozole & Temozolomide

HPLC Injection Replicates	RetentionTime (Anastrozole)	Area	Retention Time (Temozolomide)	Area
Replicate – 1	9.93	3983572	2.02	1302869
Replicate – 2	9.93	3985214	2.02	1302586
Replicate – 3	9.93	3990228	2.02	1318521
Replicate – 4	9.92	3985261	2.01	1302569
Replicate – 5	9.92	3996512	2.02	1302896
Average	9.926	3988157	2.018	1305888
Standard Deviation	0.005477	5295.407	0.004472	7063.605
% RSD	0.055181	0.132778	0.221612	0.540904

Result & Discussion: The repeatability study which was conducted on the solution having the concentration of about 100 µg/ml for Temozolomide and 100 µg/ml for Anastrozole (n =5) showed a RSD of 0.7684% for Temozolomide and 0.08488% for Anastrozole. It was concluded that the analytical technique showed good repeatability.

Intermediate precision

For intra-day studies the drug having concentration value 80%, 100 % & 120% of the target concentration (n = 3), were injected in triplicate into the HPLC system and for inter-day studies the drug at above three concentrations were injected in triplicate into the HPLC system for three days. Data were subjected to statistical treatment for the calculation of SD and RSD.

Table 8a: Data for Anastrozole analysis

Conc. Of Anastrozole (API) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Observed Conc. Of Anastrozole ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) by the proposed method			
	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Mean (n=6)	% RSD	Mean (n=6)	% RSD
10	9.94	0.96	10.43	0.97
30	30.04	0.40	30.93	0.96
100	100.91	0.93	99.15	0.19

Table 8b: Data for Temozolomide analysis

Conc. Of Temozolomide (API) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Observed Conc. Of Temozolomide ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) by the proposed method			
	Intra-Day		Inter-Day	
	Mean (n=6)	% RSD	Mean (n=6)	% RSD
10	10.09	1.54	10.13	0.46
30	30.03	0.75	30.84	0.82
100	99.94	0.48	99.37	0.91

Result and discussion:

Intraday and interday studies show that the mean RSD (%) was found to be within acceptance limit ($\leq 2\%$), so it was concluded that there was no significant difference for the assay, which was tested within day and between days. Hence, method at selected wavelength was found to be precise.

G. Limit of detection and limit of quantification

The detection limit (LOD) and quantitation limit (LOQ) may be expressed as:

$$\text{L.O.D.} = 3.3(\text{SD/S}).$$

$$\text{L.O.Q.} = 10(\text{SD/S})$$

Where, SD = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Result & Discussion

The LOD was found to be 0.02 µg/ml and 0.06 µg/ml and LOQ was found to be 0.04 µg/ml and 1.2 µg/ml for Temozolomide and Anastrozole respectively which represents that sensitivity of the method is high.

III. CONCLUSION:

A sensitive & selective stability indicating RP-HPLC method has been developed & validated for the analysis of Anastrozole & Temozolomide API.

Based on peak purity results, obtained from the analysis of samples using described method, it can be concluded that the absence of co-eluting peak along with the main peak of Anastrozole & Temozolomide indicated that the developed method is specific for the estimation of Anastrozole & Temozolomide.

Further the proposed RP-HPLC method has excellent sensitivity, precision and reproducibility.

Even though no attempt has been made to identify the degraded products proposed method can be used as a stability indicating method for assay of Anastrozole & Temozolomide in commercial formulations.

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